

Implication of Student's Misbehaviors in Class

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the implication of students' misbehavior in class. It utilized quantitative and qualitative approach in which the responses of students were classified and recorded its frequency. It collects qualitative data through phenomenal observations on students' behavior, and investigations on respondents' background. The data of this observation are in-depth discuss according to the result of investigation. Investigations reveal that students' misbehaviors imply that they have different socio-economic and learning needs. The misbehaviors they have shown is a sign that they do not find interest to learn in the classroom environment, the lessons transfer by the teachers are not align to their interest, or they need a special attention that teachers' understanding and acceptance requires.

Keywords: *students' misbehaviors, implication, socio-economic and learning needs*

INTRODUCTION

Student misbehaviors are thorny issue in daily classroom interaction (Sun and Shek, 2012). It affects the effectiveness of teachers' teaching and so with class environment and other learners. Whereas, other scenarios shown that students' misbehaviors affects time, decreased academic performance, and increased unnecessary behaviors (Bryant, et.al,2000; Weerman, Harland , et.al, 2007). Thus, this study manifests the implication of student's misbehavior in class.

Some insights on students' misbehaviors are cited by different authors. The impact of disruptive behavior could lead to class suspension which is disadvantage to teachers, school cultures, and student sides (Ford, 2013). Hwung (2016) highlighted that there is a strong initial relationship between the level of

misbehavior in a given classroom and performance evaluation. He suggested that the bulk of peer effects stem more from the academic performance of other students than from their behavior. According to Sun and Shek (2012), it is a primary importance of a teacher to identify what exactly are these behaviors inside classroom. Teachers usually reported that these disturbing behaviors in the classroom are unbearable and they had to spend a great deal of time and energy to manage the classroom (Johnson and Fullwood, 2006; Leung and Ho, 2001; Shen, et.al, 2009).

Classroom is a complex society that teachers are the role models, and interactions affect that take place between teachers and students as well as to their peers (Ratcliff, et.al, 2011). Similarly, in Pakwan Integrated School, School Year 2016-2017, one of the issues that teachers commonly raise is the misbehavior of Grade 10 students. For them, their behavior affects the teachers' activities plan; objectives of the plan were usually not carried out, and different teaching strategies were implemented but few showed effective. Most of the teachers complain on them that their misbehaviors affect also to the whole institution especially in targeting a positive academic performance. Thus, this study was employed to investigate students' misbehavior.

The proponent of this study found strength that strengthening school's curriculum could be sustained by taking a look and understanding students' misbehavior that could be a contribution in developing human capital. The unique of this study is significant in school's educational system that findings are not only base to the phenomenon observations on students' behavior but a deepen investigation on their learning and social background.

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized quantitative and qualitative approach to address the objectives of the study. It applies quantitative approach in which the responses of respondents were classified and recorded its frequency. Qualitative approach on the other hand, addressed the objectives of the study that involved collecting qualitative data through phenomenal observations and investigations on students' behaviors. The subjects of this investigation are the 19 Grade 10 students of Pakwan Integrated School, School Year 2016-2017. Hence, One (1) student was absent during the Focus Group Discussion (FGD). The data of this observation are in-depth discuss according to the result of investigation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This part presents, analyzes, and interprets the data gathered. The presentations are aided with tabular display to be clearly gleaned.

Table1. Frequency Distribution of Students' Misbehaviors Observation

Students' Behavior	Frequency	Rank
Always leaving/cutting classes and do misbehavior acts	4	2.5
Fond of playing basketball/volleyball	5	1
Act of absenteeism	2	5
Physically present but mentally absent	2	5
Participative in class or school activities and do teachers' instructions	4	2.5
Listening to class but not doing learning activities such writing notes, and solving problems	2	5
TOTAL	19	

The Table 1 presents the frequency distribution of students' misbehaviors observation. These students' behaviors are base from the observation of author as he started to investigate the class. As it shows, "*Fond of playing basketball/volleyball*" behavior is in the first rank which distribution is closely to two behaviors, "*Participative in class or school activities and do teachers' instructions*" and "*Always leaving/cutting classes and do misbehavior acts*", and followed by three (3) behaviors with same rank, "*Act of absenteeism*", "*Physically present but mentally absent*", and "*Listening to class but not doing*

learning activities such writing notes, and solving problems". These students' behaviors, except "*Participative in class or school activities and do teachers' instructions*", annoy the teachers in dealing daily class that lead to teaching-learning process problem. Hence, learning interactions, both social and instructional, have a great impact on the academic and social growth of individuals, and group dynamics of a classroom need to be analyzed to understand how teachers' best function and students best learn (Ratcliff, et.al, 2011).

Base from investigation, students who are "*Fond of playing basketball/volleyball*" are always active and participative in sports activity, and "*Always leaving/cutting classes and do misbehavior acts*" are having complex talents in arts such as dancing (modern dance), rapping music, and drawing, sketching, and lettering.

The observed "*Physically present but mentally absent*" shows that these students are having problem in family, one is raised by mother (single parent) only, and another one, parents are separated. These students observed have talents in drawing, and bottles and papers handicraft. Thus, these students are affected with the status of their parents.

The "*act of absenteeism*" behavior, investigation shows that these students are having a problem in economic background, both are too far from the school and bread winner of the family. Investigation results that these students have no teachers' problem in terms of class activities. They may have a matured mind that being a bread winner in a family is a sense of handling great responsibilities. Hence, these students may be align to leadership career.

The behavior of "*Listening to class but not doing learning activities such writing notes, and solving problems*" shows that these students are characterize as visually impaired and have learning disability. Visually impaired student found that has blurd vision that cause difficulty in reading text but this student found that has potential in drawing such as sketching anime cartoons. While, student with learning disability found that has problem on his stages of learning. Investigation shows that he was a victim of bullying, deprived from a class during his elementary grades, and stopped his elementary study for three (3) times.

The students who are “*Participative in class or school activities and do teachers’ instructions*” are evident active in class interaction and teachers’ instruction. Thus, the above mentioned students’ behavior affect to these learners. They destruct and annoy the teaching-learning process in classroom.

According to Tiwari (2014) there are various factors that cause behavior problems in the classroom such as mass media, school or family that affect the teaching learning process as it influences teacher’s ability and competence in handling the classroom environment. Hence, when behavioral problems begin to occur, it is important for teachers to react in the right way. Teachers need to learn how to teach students with behavior problems. No matter if the child is one student in a classroom with a concern or if the classroom is designed for children with these complex behavioral issues (The Room 241 Team, 2013). So, *it is a need for teachers and students to acknowledge their mutual contributions to student misbehavior. Only when both groups start to take ownership of their contribution to the problem of misbehavior can be solved* (Donetta, et.al, 2009). This is similar to the statement of Powell and Kusuma-Powell (2011) that *teachers did forge personal connections with students, often when the personality of the student and teacher were compatible or when they shared a common interest (more often than not, this was an interest in the subject the teacher was teaching).*

Table2. Students’ Preferred Tracks

Indicators	Frequency (%)	Rank
Academic	6 (33.33%)	1.5
Technical-Vocational and Livelihood (TVL)	1 (5.56%)	5
Sports	6 (33.33%)	1.5
Arts & Design	2 (11.11%)	4
Undecided	3 (16.67%)	3
Total	18 (100%)	

Table 2 is the frequency distribution classified students’ responses on their preferred interest during Focus Group Discussion (FGD). It shows two (2) tracks they preferred are in same rank, Sports and Academic. This distribution is almost similar to the result of Table1; it shows close rank of students’ misbehaviors, “*Fond of playing basketball / volleyball*” and “*Participative in class or school activities and do teachers’ instructions*”. Students who preferred “Sports” are the students who are

“*Fond of playing basketball/volleyball*”, and those who preferred to “Academic” Tracks are those who are “*Participative in class or school activities and do teachers’ instructions*”

The “Undecided” track is closely related to students whose behavior is “*Listening to class but not doing learning activities such writing notes, and solving problems*”. This implication does not mean that these students have no ability or talents. Hence, these students are have talents as explained in Table 1 but not expose or involve in school activities. Perhaps, they just need a help from teachers to discover their potentials and interests (Swift, 2012).

The students who preferred “Arts and Design” Track are one of the students who are always leaving/cutting classes and do misbehavior acts, and another one is one of the students who is “Physically present but mentally absent”.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Students’ misbehavior in learning environment proved that everybody learns in different way. The behaviors that observed and shown in group is a sign that they need in learning process that align to their learning way and interest. Teachers should cater programs that relevant to their interests where they have given an opportunity to pursue their learning needs. With such mentoring and support, students may reach their potential (Serra, 2017). Thus, accept the students in his/her own way, capacity, and ability (NOVA, 2017).

REFERENCES CITED

1. Bryant, A. L., Schulenberg, J., Bachman, J. G., O’Malley, P. M., and Johnston, L. D. (2000) “Understanding the links among school misbehavior, academic achievement, and cigarette use: a national panel study of adolescents,” *Prevention Science*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 71–87, 2000. View at Google Scholar · View at Scopus
2. Donetta J. Cothran, Pamela Hodges Kulinna & Deborah A. Garrahy (2009). *Attributions for and consequences of student misbehavior*. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/17408980701712148>
3. Ford, Mike (2013). *The Impact of Disruptive Students in Wisconsin Public Schools*. Retrieved from <https://www.badgerinstitute.org/Reports/2013/The>

- Impact-of-Disruptive-Students-in-Wisconsin-Public-Scho on July 5, 2016
4. Hwung, Alex (2016). PEER MI SBEHAVIOR EFFECTS IN THE CLAS SROOM. Retrieved from http://scholarship.claremont.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2458&context=cmc_theses on August 02, 2016
 5. Johnson, H. L. and Fullwood, H. L. (2006), "Disturbing behaviors in the secondary classroom: how do general educators perceive problem behaviors?" *Journal of Instructional Psychology*, vol. 33, no. 1, pp. 20–39, 2006. View at Google Scholar
 6. Leung, J. and Ho, C. (2001) "Disruptive classroom behavior perceived by Hong Kong primary school teachers," *Journal of Educational Research*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 223–237, 2001. View at Google Scholar
 7. NOVA (2017). My Brother's Case: Detecting Attention and Learning Disabilities in Children. *Health and Home*, The National Journal (March-April 2017), page 36-37
 8. Powell, William and Kusuma-Powell, Ochan (2011). How to Teach Now. Retrieved from <http://www.ascd.org/publications/books/111011/chapters/knowning-our-students-as-learners.aspx> on July 29, 2016
 9. Ratcliff, Nancy J.; Jones, Cathy R.; Costner, Richard H.; Savage-David, Emma; Hunt, Gilbert H. (2011). The Impact of Misbehavior on Classroom Climate *Education Digest: Essential Readings Condensed for Quick Review*, v77 n2 p16-20 Oct 2011)
 10. Serra, Arnold (2017). Personal Answers: Motivation minus the Pressure. *Health and Home*, The National Journal (March-April 2017), page 19
 11. Shen, J., Zhang, N., Zhang, C., Caldarella, P., Richardson, M.J., and Shatzer, R.H. (2009) "Chinese elementary school teachers' perceptions of students' classroom behaviour problems," *Educational Psychology*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 187–201, 2009. View at Publisher · View at Google Scholar · View at Scopus
 12. Sun, Rachel C. F., and Shek, Daniel T.L. (2012). Student Classroom Misbehavior: An Exploratory Study Based on Teachers' Perceptions. *Scientific World Journal*. 2012; 2012: 208907. Published online 2012 Aug 1. doi: 10.1100/2012/208907
 13. Swift, Jackie (2012). Teacher Network Teacher's blog. Just what is gifted and talented?: A guide to supporting students with potential that is way above average. Retrieved from <https://www.theguardian.com/teacher-network/teacher-blog/2012/may/09/teaching-gifted-and-talented-pup> on August 20, 2016
 14. The Room 241 Team (2013). Strategies for Teaching Students with Behavioral Problems. Retrieved from <https://education.cu-portland.edu/blog/classroom-resources/strategies-for-teaching-students-with-behavior> on July 10, 2016
 15. Tiwari, Gyanendra (2014). A Study on the classroom behaviour Problems at secondary level.. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/269710972_A_Study_on_the_classroom_behaviour_Problems_at_secondary_level [accessed Jul 01 2018].
 16. Weerman, F. M., Harland, P., and van der Laan, P. H. (2007). "Misbehavior at school and delinquency elsewhere: a complex relationship," *Criminal Justice Review*, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 358–379, 2007. View at Publisher · View at Google Scholar · View at Scopus